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Data management plan (DMP)

Topologically Accurate Segmentation and Brain MRI Generation

topo_seg

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1.0	30-11-2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.17771378 .
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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
BraTS	Brain Tumor Segmentation (challenge)
IXI	Information eXtraction from Images dataset
BIDS	Brain Imaging Data Structure
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	topo-seg project data	Structured text, Source code, Other		20 - 50 GB	no

Description for "topo-seg project data":

This dataset will contain all the files created within the project : code (.py and .ipynb), model checkpoints (.pth), preprocessed and generated images (.nii.gz)

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	BraTS 2021	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dschettler8845/brats-2021-task1		no
R2	IXI Dataset	https://brain-development.org/ixi-dataset/		no

Description for "BraTS 2021":

This dataset includes brain MRI scans of adult brain glioma patients, comprising of 4 structural modalities (i.e., T1, T1c, T2, T2-FLAIR) and their associated manually generated ground truth labels for each tumor sub-region (segmentation masks). These scans are a collection of data from existing TCIA collections, but also cases provided by individual institutions and willing to share with a CC BY license. The total size of the dataset is about 12.4GB. No DOI is provided.

Description for "IXI Dataset":

This dataset contains 600 MR images from healthy subjects, available in NIFTI format, including T1 and T2 images, along with the associated bvecs and bvals files and demographic information in a spreadsheet. The data were collected across three hospitals in London: Hammersmith Hospital using a Philips 3T system, Guy's Hospital using a Philips 1.5T system, and the Institute of Psychiatry using a GE 1.5T system, although detailed scan parameters are not currently available for the latter. The data are distributed under the Creative Commons CC BY-SA 3.0 license. The total size of the dataset (of T1 and T2 images) is about 8.1GB. No DOI is provided.

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Both the BRATS 2021 and IXI datasets will be reused to train a two-stage neural network pipeline for generating topologically accurate brain MRIs with gliomas. BRATS 2021 provides multimodal MRIs with tumor segmentations, used to train the segmentation diffusion model and evaluate anatomical accuracy. IXI provides healthy T1 and T2 images to ensure normal brain structures are preserved. Both datasets will be preprocessed to standardize voxel sizes, dimensions, and intensity, keeping only the images required for the pipeline (namely T1 and T2 images). Python libraries, including MONAI and PyTorch, will be used for preprocessing, model training, and inference. The project will generate three types of data : code, models, and images. The code consists of Python scripts and Jupyter notebooks (.py and .ipynb) for preprocessing the raw datasets then for training, testing and running the pipeline. The models include trained network weights and checkpoints saved as PyTorch files (.pth). The images include synthetic segmentation masks and synthetic MRIs generated by the pipeline, saved in NIfTI format (.nii.gz) and organized according to the pipeline stage by which they were generated.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

Data will be organized in a hierarchical structure. The main categories will be : raw data from the original datasets, preprocessed data, generated data, models, and code. Raw and preprocessed images from BRATS 2021 and IXI will be stored in subject-specific folders organized by modality. Filenames will use lowercase letters and underscores according to the pattern sub-`<id>_<modality>.nii.gz` (e.g., sub-00001_t1w.nii.gz), with metadata file sub-`<id>_<modality>.json`. Synthetic images will be of the format sub-synth`<id>_<modality>.nii.gz` (e.g., sub-synth001_t1w.nii.gz). Model checkpoints will be saved as `diffusion_version_epoch<xx>.pth` or `controlnet_version_epoch<xx>.pth`. Code files will be lowercase-named .py scripts or .ipynb notebooks.

Metadata will follow the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard where applicable. In the raw data directory, for each of the two datasets, a JSON file will summarize the dataset titles, authors, licenses and links to the original source. For each real image in the preprocessed files directory, a JSON file will include the preprocessing steps and their parameters, and provenance information linking it to the raw dataset. For synthetic images, the JSON file will instead include the model type, training epoch, and pipeline parameters used to generate each file. Model checkpoints will be accompanied by a JSON file that describes the parameters and epoch.

The repository-level README will explain how to reproduce the results, including dependencies, how to call each model file to generate synthetic images, and persistent links for large files stored on the TU Wien test repository.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture, data entry validation and - automated versioning - consistency of random seeds.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

All the files (including both code and large files) will be on the TU Wien (test) repository, and a backup of the code will be kept on Git. Each Git commit or tag will correspond to a specific snapshot or version of the data and models on the TU Wien repository, so anyone using the Git repository can identify exactly which datasets and checkpoints to download from TU Wien to reproduce the results.

DOI for the TU Wien repository : [10.70124/9e01q-cek89](https://doi.org/10.70124/9e01q-cek89)

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

The data from the original datasets have been anonymized by the organizations that generated them.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: BraTS : BraTS consortium and original contributors IXI : IXI project Preprocessed datasets, code, models, generated images : project owner (Rim Faroudy) via TU Wien (test) repository

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-12-01	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Users will need : - Python and an IDE - Python libraries : Nibabel (or similar) to read .nii.gz files. PyTorch and MONAI libraries for the data acquisition and model training. numpy and os libraries for more basic tasks that are needed for the project. All necessary dependencies, environment specifications, and instructions will be documented in requirements.txt and the repository-level README.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The main target audience is researchers in machine learning for healthcare. Given the scarcity of real medical images for brain tumor segmentation, this project aims to augment datasets in order to train more powerful models for image segmentation.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Principal Investigator will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.